

MESS 0018¹

GEO 2.2 - Electogeology evidence in macrolytic magnetic and gravitic field anomalies² in VA, NC, and KY associated with surface gravity anomalies

Sf. R. Careaga, BSEE, MSTOM

October 2022

Best Viewed at: <https://bit.ly/3MsAJLU>

ABSTRACT

This paper examines USGS and other mainstream produced magnetic and gravity anomalies, comparing with earthquake and precipitation data. Arguments are made/found for direct arc EDM in an electrogeological framework as proposed by Steinbacher, Thornhill-Jupp-Hall, Yelverton-Gable, Burke and Careaga, et al.

Keywords: Gravity - Magnetism - Anomalies - EDM - Pine Mountain - Blue Ridge - Big South Fork

¹ This paper breaks the 5-page MESS standard, however, it is the best format for the work; most of the space is graphic

² Figure 1: Gravity anomalies in USA; colored arrows and highlights added; credit: Gravity Map Services

http://gravityservices.com/?page_id=92

Key

- Black Circle - clear anomaly unrelated to elevation change in midwest
- Pink Arrows - discussed anomalies in this paper
- Red arrow - Knobs Region Lichtenburgs
- Cyan Arrow - Cumberland Gap, as part of the “crooked smile” of the Pine Mountain flux
- Purple Arrow - Actual location of the uplifted Blue Ridge Mountains flux

Magnetic Anomalies

Figure 2 Magnetic Anomalies; credit: USGS³

It is important to note the following:

- ❖ Moving left to right in the pink arrows, we see the New Madrid Fault, the Big South Fork (of the Daniel Boone leyline, lower terminus, the Red River Gorge (negative) anomaly nearby the inexplicable increase in rainfall (see figure 3), and the Great Serpent Mound astrobleme (region) terminus; you can tell this is the DB leyline and not Pine Mtn or Blue Ridge because of the angle of incline
- ❖ The Orange arrow indicates only (for this paper) that an electrical and thereby electrogravitic anomaly is represented by magnetic remnant, probably from the R. Burkian Great Lakes terminus event, which would have been foundational (perhaps a Hall Vortex) in the Shamash (genesis/formation) era, pre Atlantean Period. Perhaps even pre-Pleistocene.
- ❖ The Purple arrow indicates the Blue Ridge leyline flow, and there is an interesting negative (anode) “burn spot” that looks suspiciously close to Ashland, NC, and it would be interesting to study that more deeply

³ <https://pubs.usgs.gov/of/1999/ofr-99-0557/html/magnetic.jpg>

Figure 3 - Average Annual Precipitation (Kentucky), credit: Spatial Climate Analysis Service/OSU⁴

Again looking at the Magnetic map, as a whole (see the following page) we see incredible fluctuations at key (state park and national park related) locations, which have in themselves multiple electrogeological significance, in that hypothesis, and in fact (in some cases). Few of the locations have the level of class A evidence as at Ship rock or Garden of the Gods (IL/Hicks Dome). The two or three areas that have class A certification, within Kentucky, have also different displays to their fluctuation:

Moving left to right with the orange arrows (see figure 4):

1. The Big South Fork/Canyonlands (west of) area has a strong anode/cathode presentation
2. The Knobs region lichtenburg has a strong “escarpment” of the magnetic field
3. The Wildcat Mountain/Red Bird region has also a strong escarpment, and this detail should be overlaid with the www.hiddendestinationsky.com map to look for natural and geological evidence, assuming, of course that this portion of the DBNF leyline is acting as a cathode in a sinusoidal presentation. Close to this region, and certainly at the Red River Gorge there are (as reported elsewhere) electrogeological evidentiary sandstone speciae that cannot be overlooked. It is Grade A- evidence⁵, as compared to Garden of the Gods (Grade A+ evidence), but quite quality, nevertheless.

⁴ <https://myviewfromthewoods.com/kentucky/>

⁵ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/volunteer/grades>

Figure 4 - Magnetic Anomalies - detailed map; credit: USGS⁶

⁶ https://pubs.usgs.gov/of/2002/ofr-02-361/edited_usa_only.jpg

Finally, looking at that last figure the magnetic anomalies east of the Blue Ridge mountains are impossible to defend from a non-magma/basalt perspective. They can't have it both ways. Either the area was heavily volcanic and now is not, or the area was EDM formed. We can see from the next section, more evidence for the latter.

Gravity Anomalies

Figure 5 - Gravity Anomalies; particularly east of the Blue Ridge Mountains, at the Big South Fork of KY/TN, and at the New Madrid Zone in far western KY/MO junction, with marked gravity escarpment at the Knobs region lichtenburg (orange arrow)⁷, despite the mildly raised elevation. Credit: chegg.com

Please bear in mind the DBNF leyline gravity anomaly is interesting in two ways:

1. The Cathode flux at the Big South Fork extends, for unknown reasons north, through the middle of the Knobs region (which arcs around the Ordovician limestone dome) up into the KY River⁸ Palisades region
2. The Anode escarpment at the Red River Gorge where the Aether flux is definitely highest, but twin to the Big South Fork⁹

⁷ Note the blue region terminates at or near a) the Jephtha Knob bolid/cryptoexplosive astrobleme and b) the Big Sink Perattian Thunderbolt cryptoexplosive site, and c) may connect to the Fort Knox salt/upheaval dome

⁸ Second oldest riverbed in the world (Devonian)

⁹ McCreary Co. has over 500 windows and arches, and so does the Red River Gorge/Natural Bridge area; both have a picturesque "Natural Arch"

Figure 6 - credit: S. Snyder¹⁰ & Figure 7 - Geology Resources; credit: VA Energy¹¹

As imperfect as this overlay method is, we can see the interesting magnetic anomaly issue **clearly**. The Blue Ridge leyline, typified by Mesozoic, is primarily **WEST** of the magnetic region one expects is related to the mountains! And it is not valley related, as is seen the large magnetic escarpment overlays the magnetic anomaly, as well.

More importantly, look at the bipolar gravity anomaly **NORTH** of the terminus of the Shenandoah National Park, at the edge of the Blue Ridge mountains! This is not possible through coincidence, and it is really ill-defined from a volcanology perspective, why the magnetic signature would behave bipolar in the plains of North Virginia. The most interesting anomalies, as well, seem to be occurring over the plains east of the mountains, and not in the crystalline matrix of the Mesozoic basins.

Look at the materials of the Piedmont Belts:

Table 1 - Mineral Resources of Virginia's Piedmont Belts

<i>Industrial</i>	<i>Metals</i>	<i>Stone</i>	<i>Aggregate</i>
Feldspar, Mica, Kyanite, Vermiculite, Barite	Iron, Mn, Copper, Gold, Pyrite, Tungsten	Granite, Slate, Marble	

¹⁰ https://pubs.usgs.gov/of/2005/1052/images/va_grav200opt1.jpg

¹¹ <https://www.energy.virginia.gov/geology/geologymineralresources.shtml>

Figure 7 overlaid with Figure 8 - magnetic anomalies of VA; credit: Nature¹²

Comparing mineralization and resources with magnetic anomalies is very clearly indicative of electromagnetic (telluric) flux within various crystal matrices.

- The magnetic escarpments, and the valley formations (Shenandoah) clearly align.
- The minerals in the Mesozoic and the magnetic flux are also directly correlated.
- Magnetic turbulence directly overlaps the Blue Ridge flux.
- The difference of the Appalachian plateau with Blue Ridge, in terms of magnetism, is more clearly indicated; this reflects the difference in macrolytics experience of the telluric with the DBNF flux and Appalachian plateau¹³.

¹² <https://www.nature.com/articles/nrn1745>

¹³ It is probably that the Appalachians were produced from upthrust of plate tectonics, perhaps some very ancient volcanism. But they are quite different from the other mentioned regions.

Complete Bouguer Gravity Anomaly Map of Virginia

by Stephen L. Snyder

Copyright © 2005 Nature Publishing Group

Nature Reviews | Neuroscience

Figure 8 (gif) & 9 - As anyone can see, there is not a 1:1 between the magnetic and gravitic anomaly map! Med Qual: <https://makeagif.com/i/Plw0Ej>

Electrogeological Explanations

Radiative Energy

Figure 10 - US heatflow map; credit: S. Gao¹⁴

Could the radiative heat flux be directly related? Or could this affect the gravity or magnetic anomalies? Quite likely, but more work will be needed, with direct overlay, and a means to discount or account for the air flow and meteorological flux and pattern (climate) in the areas.

Earthquake Data

Figure 11 - Earthquake Data and possible connections with lithospheric Magnetic Field data; credit: Lei et al.¹⁵

Compare the map on left (New Madrid Zone) with the data in figure 5. More work is needed, but it seems that Figure 1 has much of this relationship. Figure 3 is also important. This will be **deeply** explored in MESS0019¹⁶.

¹⁴ https://web.mst.edu/~sgao/maps/us_heatflow.jpg

¹⁵ <https://earth-planets-space.springeropen.com/articles/10.1186/s40623-018-0949-7>

¹⁶ <https://bit.ly/3VfLWDk>

EDM - as an arc discharge event (uplift)

Looking at the Yelverton¹⁷-Gable¹⁸ laboratory data, comparing with the Thornhill-Hall¹⁹-Steinbacher²⁰ model, picked up by Burke²¹ & Hawthorne Jr.^{22 23}, and confirmed by the author in discovery of multiple locations^{24 25 26} ... we see the uplift of the Knobs, Pine Mtn flux, and Blue Ridge chain as direct (potential) evidence of **direct arc electric discharge machining** evidence in electrogeology. It is unclear, though, how much of this is electric field related, and also, how to *specifically* (not generally) model the anode-cathode circuit connections. Propositions from Hall^{27 28} and Burke are worth considering in comparison to Yelverton & Gable, as well as to Jupp²⁹ et al.

Conclusions & Suggestions

The correlation of the gravity and magnetic maps is indicative of an EDM pattern, and defiant of a magma chamber matrix. Furthermore, the correlation of gravity anomalies with weather behavior is stronger in many ways than correlation between mountainous/mineral deposition and magnetic anomalies. This is incredibly surprising, but considering the facets of electrogeology evidence in KY and VA, etc. we are not too surprised. More suggestions for this research include:

- Research into the Tornado behaviors in western KY
- Relationships of precipitation and Mag/Grav anomalies in KY, where data is available.
- Detailed overlays for the Big South Fork, Pine Mountain (crooked smile), and upper Blue Ridge flux
- Study of magnetic escarpments looking for anode or cathode removal behaviors in these locations; working in conjunction with A. Hall & P.M. Jupp
- Detailed work in New Madrid zone regarding anomalies and earthquake data
- Comparison of VA anomalies with magma studies, looking for potential kimberlites
 - And comparison with Carolina Bay activity
- Study of the per-Knobs "karst" topography of Kentucky
- Detailed examination of the Wildcat Mountain/Red Bird regions looking for dense energy flux explanations in anomaly data.

The author hopes that within the GEO 2.2 framework to provide significant evidence for electrogeological formations, in situ. Preferably with mineral speciation for direct comparison.

¹⁷ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/researchers/electrogeology/yelverton>

¹⁸ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/researchers/electrogeology/gable>

¹⁹ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/researchers/electrogeology/a-hall>

²⁰ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/researchers/electrogeology/m-steinbacher>

²¹ The Electric View - Electric Landscapes - TEV Live

²² <https://www.iijsci.org/journal/pdv/sci/pdfs/ZA014LF20r.pdf>

²³ History of Electric Geology

²⁴

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/332831733_Proposed_Discovery_of_Perattian_Thunderbolt_of_the_Gods_Strike_Location_in_Versailles_KY_Comparison_of_Predicted_Models_and_LiDAR_scans_of_Big_Sink_location_in_Woodford_County_Addendum_for_Plasmaglyph

²⁵ https://www.academia.edu/49456803/Trip_Report_Pebble_Beach_Red_River_Gorge

²⁶ https://www.academia.edu/81402498/Trip_Report_Shiprock_and_Barringer_Crater

²⁷ Andrew Hall: The Arc-Blasted Earth | EU2016

²⁸ Andrew Hall: The Keystone Pattern | Thunderbolts

²⁹ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/researchers/electrogeology/jupp>

References

1. "Gravity and Magnetic Data Brokerage," GMS/Gravity Map Service, 2013, http://gravityservices.com/?page_id=92
2. "Hidden Destinations" Sf. R. Careaga, https://www.google.com/maps/d/viewer?mid=1hldTpY8nuJDjRws1PI5iLbLWJDM&hl=en_US&ll=38.01520770656196%2C-84.59047807023916&z=10
3. "Does North Carolina, Arkansas, & Kentucky Receive Too Much Rainfall?" myviewfromthewoods.com, T. Marsh Affiliates, 2021, <https://myviewfromthewoods.com/kentucky/>
4. "Grades," (EPEMC) Gateway/The Pulse, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/volunteer/grades>
5. "Geology and Mineral Resources," Virginia Energy, 2021, <https://www.energy.virginia.gov/geology/geologymineralresources.shtml>
6. "The physics and neurobiology of magnetoreception," Nature Reviews Neuroscience, S.Johnsen & K.J. Lohmann, 2005, <https://www.nature.com/articles/nrn1745>
7. "Possible correlation between the vertical component of lithospheric magnetic field and continental seismicity," Earth, Planets and Space volume 70, Article number: 179, Y. Lei, L. Jiao & H. Chen, 2018, <https://earth-planets-space.springeropen.com/articles/10.1186/s40623-018-0949-7>
8. "MESS0019: MET 2.1 - KY Tornadoe New Madrid Zone & magnetics," Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1uD7wGiQXggXemKmAg1wAvcl9BY9lsG6yz763-4OEL0g/edit>
9. "B. Yelverton," (EPEMC) Gateway/ The Pulse, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/researchers/electrogeology/yelverton>
10. "J. Gable: ElectroTerraVision," (EPEMC) Gateway/ The Pulse, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/researchers/electrogeology/gable>
11. "A. Hall: Electrogeologist," (EPEMC) Gateway/ The Pulse, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022 <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/researchers/electrogeology/a-hall>
12. Michael Steinbacher: THE Electrogeologist," (EPEMC) Gateway/ The Pulse, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/researchers/electrogeology/m-steinbacher>
13. "The Electric View - Electric Landscapes - TEV Live," Youtube/The Electric View, 2019, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vIFqAAXTxaM>
14. "Electric Discharge - Not an Impact Caused Formation Of Upheaval Dome, Canyonlands National Park, Utah (Extended)," Systemics, Cybernetics and Informatics Volume 18 # 4, R. Hawthorne, 2020, <https://www.iiisci.org/journal/pdv/sci/pdfs/ZA014LF20r.pdf>
15. "History of Electric Geology," Youtube/Electric Universe Eyes, L. White & R. Hawthorne, 2022, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=i0YMkrhZXLy>
16. Proposed Discovery of Perattian Thunderbolt of the Gods Strike Location in Versailles, KY Comparison of Predicted Models and LiDAR scans of Big Sink location in Woodford County; Addendum for Plasmaglyphs and the Megafauna Extinction" Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2019, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/332831733_Proposed_Discovery_of_Perattian_Thunderbolt_of_the_Gods_Strike_Location_in_Versailles_KY_Comparison_of_Predicted_Models_and_LiDAR_scans_of_Big_Sink_location_in_Woodford_County_Addendum_for_Plasmaglyph
17. "Trip Report: Pebble Beach, Red River Gorge," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021, https://www.academia.edu/49456803/Trip_Report_Pebble_Beach_Red_River_Gorge
18. "Trip Report: Shiprock & Barringer Crater," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, https://www.academia.edu/81402498/Trip_Report_Shiprock_and_Barringer_Crater
19. "The Arc-Blasted Earth," Youtube/Thunderbolts Project, A. Hall, 2016, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fDIRMB3hVQM>
20. "The Keystone Pattern," Youtube/Thunderbolts Project, A. Hall, 2022, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HdfBGqWpW5w>